

PROBLEMS OF INCREASING LEGAL INFORMATION AND LEGAL LITERACY OF YOUTH

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Annotation: The article explores the problems of increasing the legal awareness and legal literacy of young people and ways to solve them.

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It is known from world experience that every nation has its own spiritual heritage, mentality and values. The legal consciousness of the nation is also considered as such an asset. States, determining the paths of development, follow the path of exalting the spiritual heritage, traditions, values, as well as national legal consciousness. Because a high level of legal consciousness controls the democratic processes in the country. It ensures the triumph of peace and human rights.

By decision of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a program of measures to improve the legal culture in society was developed and approved. According to the program, the task was set to organize training courses on human rights, women's rights, children's rights in higher educational institutions and training centers for retraining and advanced training of personnel. It is also planned to study the scientific foundations of improving legal culture [1].

On September 14, 2019, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 406 "On State Policy on Youth" was adopted. The law establishes that educational organizations, together with law enforcement agencies, participate in activities to improve the legal awareness and legal culture of young people, as well as their spiritual and moral education [2].

Many issues have been identified that need to be resolved in 2022-2023 in order to improve the legal culture in society. In particular, it is planned to hold the events "Month of legal literacy", "Month of the fight against corruption", "Month of constitutional rights" to form legal education in the family and educational institutions. Measures have also been identified, such as teaching young people the minimum requirements for legal literacy and assessing their legal knowledge[3].

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan instructed to form legal immunity to factors that negatively affect the legal education of young people in the country,

compliance with laws, loyalty to national values, fostering a sense of intolerance for violations [4].

More than 60 percent of the population of Uzbekistan is under 30 years old. Some of them, aged 14 to 30, make up the so-called youth social stratum. The President of Uzbekistan spoke about the need to start raising the legal awareness and legal culture of the population from childhood and instructed to develop it throughout life. Practice shows that the beginning of deep visualization and broad observation of acquired legal knowledge falls on the youthful period of a person's life, that is, between 14-30 years. It is during this period that a person begins to feel his rights and freedoms as an individual. He wants to take his place in society. This age period is considered a favorable period for the legal education and training of young people, improving their legal knowledge, skills and qualifications, increasing their legal awareness and culture.

Some jurists consider legal consciousness to be the possession of all legal concepts. There are also views on legal consciousness as a concept that includes legal mentality and legal ideology [5]. However, the reflection of legal knowledge in the imagination of a person and the formation of new knowledge in it is the essence of legal consciousness.

Legal consciousness means a set of ideas, knowledge, information and feelings that express people's attitude to the legal system, legislation and other (real and ideal) legal phenomena[6].

Legal consciousness is formed under the influence of the inner spirit and psyche of a person, which are formed on the basis of moral values, conclusions drawn by him from the events around him, knowledge received by him as a result of education. Legal consciousness, formed first by family members, then by the social environment and employees of educational organizations, is not always perfect.

The legal disciplines taught in educational institutions have a certain influence on the development of the legal consciousness of young people. Young people have certain ideas about their rights and freedoms. Legal sciences attract students with the essence of law, the legal system, legal norms, responsibility, and the concepts of punishment. Warns of the grave consequences of crimes and socially dangerous acts.

The rise of legal consciousness depends on legal literacy. Because the development of literacy accelerates the improvement of legal consciousness. Legal educators and law enforcement officers have a great influence on raising

the level of legal literacy of young people. Because experts in the field of jurisprudence can very intelligibly explain to others the intricacies of the system. It is possible to increase the level of legal literacy of young people by familiarizing them with the law and regulations.

Practice proves that legal activities carried out in educational institutions serve to improve the legal literacy of young people. With this in mind, regular meetings with representatives of law enforcement agencies are included in the plans of moral and ethical events organized in educational institutions. From such meetings, young people receive relevant conclusions. Competitions aimed at improving the legal knowledge of students in schools and other educational institutions will also be of great importance. The audience will get a great impression from the performances presented in it. Knowledge in questions and answers also has a positive effect on legal literacy. But such events, meetings, conversations are not enough to improve legal literacy. Because it will be difficult to achieve high results.

In order to reduce crime in the country, to form youth intolerance towards crime, it is advisable to consistently implement the tasks set in state programs. In state programs, all power structures are assigned the appropriate tasks to improve the legal awareness and literacy of young people. The execution of tasks is systematically monitored. At the same time, each state body, state institutions, non-governmental non-profit organizations, the general public work together to improve the legal literacy of young people.

The reforms carried out in Uzbekistan, as in the developed countries of the world, are aimed at developing a free legal state and a just civil society. Achieving the ultimate goal requires serious tasks. In particular, in order to achieve certain results, it is necessary to develop the legal awareness and legal literacy skills of young people. Young people with a high level of legal awareness and legal literacy determine the future of the country. They understand that the rights and freedoms of others must be protected on the basis of their knowledge of their rights.

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